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Title:

**Domesticity: self-punishment and catharsis
—"Home as Hell" in cinema and literature**

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Abstract

The domestic universe has been largely explored in the fields of cinema and literature as a backdrop for political, racial, religious, sexual, and social oppressions. Notorious types of these phenomena are related with domestic abuse and violence in many forms. Mostly inflicted — psychologically or physically— by a group or a person towards others. The present paper is rather focused in another perspective of action in the realm of the domestic: the self-imposed punishment and its ulterior catharsis.

Fictional characters of outcasts, misfits, and renegades are often depicted in the reclusion of their homes —an operative method to emphasize their positioning towards society: e.g. alienation or defiance. Debatably, *common people*, too. Analyzing Freud's and Klein's formulations on *self-punishment*, this text will argue that such reclusion shouldn't be always perceived as a safe-place but rather a penitence. From modernist literature to modern cinema, authors have created a plenitude of cases in which a house is the mental and spatial *locus* of individual or collective struggles. Having the self-imposed condition as the common denominator, some specific examples are analyzed and compared. What can be learnt about domesticity from Dostoyevsky's *'Notes from the Underground'* and Mike Leigh's *'Naked'*? From Chantal Akerman's distinctive reflective apartment atmospheres? From Marco Ferreri's grotesque fanfare in *'The Big Feast'* or Luis Buñuel's collective irrationality displayed in *'El Angel Exterminador'*?

In different ways and for distinctive reasons —nihilism, nostalgia, surrealism, revenge—, domesticity is amplified "as" or "by" self-punishment. Domestic space becomes the *mise-en-scène* for confinement, denial, despair, madness, paranoia, refusal, unacceptance. A tumultuous, cathartic path in which characters seek some sort of atonement. In some cases the house is a protagonist, in others an uncanny, anonymous, presence. At the end, through a sequence of textual and visual interpretations, this essay will provide a theoretical context on how these authors subverted the preconception of "home as haven" into "home as hell".

Keywords: *domesticity; spatial analysis; image interpretation*
